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Music Teachers' Burnout Levels in terms of Some Variables

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Abstract

The disappointments of Nurse Jones, who is well-known by education researchers working in burnout have been seen frequently among teachers in recent years. Research results show that, contrary to the established perception existing in society, music teachers are one of the groups that experience burnout most heavily. The international literature offers a rich knowledge on this subject. However, in Turkey, the literature in which we can discuss the subject has not yet matured. There is a need for empirical research on the subject. The purpose of the study is to examine whether the burnout levels of music teachers differ according to gender, seniority, institution, and participation in in-service training. The study, structured according to the survey model, was carried out with 48 music teachers. The data were obtained using the Personal Information Form and Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey. ANOVA, Kruskal-Wallis, t-test, and Mann-Whitney U test were used for data analysis. The results showed that music teachers' burnout was not differed according to gender, seniority, institution, and participation in in-service training.

Keywords: Music Teachers, Burnout, Gender, Seniority, Institution, In-Service Training

1. Introduction

Burnout is one of the current themes used to explain the problems faced by teachers who represent one of the most strategic organizations of societies. Although the concept; was processed in a few studies until the 1970s, it was first introduced into the academic literature by clinical psychologist H. J. Freudenberger (Maslach & Schaufeli, 2017; Maslach, Schaufeli, & Leiter, 2001). Freudenberger defines the concept of burnout that he uses to explain the process of loss of motivation and commitment; as “to fail, wear out, or become exhausted by making excessive demands on energy, strength, or resources” (Freudenberger, 1974, p. 159). The first comprehensive studies on the subject were conducted by social psychologist Maslach. Maslach argues that the stress and coping strategies experienced by people working in jobs that have a direct relationship with people have significant effects on professional identity and work behavior. According to Maslach, burnout “is a psychological syndrome that occurs due to chronic work stress and manifests itself in the form of exhaustion,

cynicism and low work productivity” (Maslach & Leiter, 2007, p. 368). Maslach handled burnout with a multidimensional structure and conceptualized it as emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and personal accomplishment. Existing models, especially the Maslach Model, have formed the theoretical basis of many scientific studies that contribute to our analysis of teacher burnout. Clinical studies in the 1970s and systematic research conducted after the 1980s thanks to scales developed specifically for the subject have enabled to create of rich literature. The current knowledge provides important findings of the presence, causes, and consequences of teacher burnout, and forms a reliable basis on which we can discuss in depth.

1.1 Teacher Burnout

Teacher burnout; is a complex problem that needs to be addressed from a broad perspective and is associated with many organizational, social, and individual variables (Ballantyne & Retell, 2020; Lens & Jesus, 1999; McLain, 2005). For example; while factors such as organizational discrimination, mobbing, and external control increase teacher burnout (Alkan, 2011; Byrne, 1994; Çelik, 2011); it is seen that organizational commitment, organizational trust, organizational justice, positive organizational climate, effective and democratic class management, perceived executive support and social support reduce burnout (Durak & Seferoğlu, 2017; Karataş, 2009; Polatcan, Cansoy, & Kılıç, 2019). In addition to these results; factors such as undesirable student behavior (Baysal, 1995; Durak & Seferoğlu, 2017; Hastings & Bham 2003; Mancini, 2008; Polatcan et al., 2019; Şahin, 2007), role conflict and role (Baysal, 1995; Byrne, 1994; Cunningham, 1983; Friedman, 1993; İnce, 2014; Kyriacou, 1987), work overload, crowded classes, inadequate physical conditions, negative school and classroom climate, limiting participation in decision-making processes, poor support from managers and colleagues (Baysal, 1995; Byrne, 1999; Girgin, 1995; Polatcan et al., 2019; Şahin, 2007; Tümkaya, 1996), low motivation (Byrne, 1994), the inability of the organization to meet teacher demands (Farber, 1984) and low salary policies (Baysal, 1995; Hamann, Daugherty, & Sherbon, 1988; Mancini, 2008; Tümkaya, 1996), etc. are also known to have an effect on teacher burnout.

The above factors, which are shown as the source of teacher burnout, cause negative attitudes and behaviors in teachers, and this situation can be reflected in the teaching processes. Related research shows that teacher burnout; has a series of results including psychological such as depression, anger, emotional instability, anxiety, rejection of emotions, self-incrimination, pessimism, wrath, alienation, disappointment, paranoia, difficulty with attention/focus, reduced ability to cope with stress, despair, loss of self-esteem (Farber, 1984; Hamann & Daugherty, 1985), etc. and behavioral such as absenteeism, low job performance, carelessness in planning lessons, low tolerance to students, weakness in classroom discipline, conflict with the social environment, inability to retain the energy or enthusiasm required for effective teaching (Farber, 1984; Hamann, Daugherty, & Mills, 1987; Lens & Jesus, 1999; McLain, 2005), etc. These results raise the concern that teacher burnout will become increasingly common in educational institutions and that it will cause irreparable harm to education systems, especially unless some organizational measures are taken. For this reason, the resolution of teacher burnout, which is defined as a dangerous occupational disease, is important in both individual and social contexts.

1.2 Burnout in the Music Teaching Profession

Music teaching is one of the branches which has intense burnout, stress, high attrition rates, and dangerous leaving rates from the system (Figueras, 2014; Hodge, Jupp, & Taylor, 1994; Kertz-Welzel, 2009; US National Center for Education Statistics [NCfES], 1997; Robertson, 1986). In a study conducted with the participation of 3200 music teachers in the USA, it was found that 52% of the teachers experienced burnout (Texas Music Educators Association [TMEA], 2016). There are also findings showing that music teachers experience emotional exhaustion and depersonalization despite their high perception of personal accomplishment (Figueras, 2014; Hendry, 2001; Hodge et al., 1994; McLain, 2005; Nimmo, 1986). Many organizational and individual factors such as lack of student motivation and discipline, salary, crowded classes, workload, manager apathy, role ambiguity, budget insufficiency, etc. leading to teacher burnout, in generalisable nature; are also valid for music teachers (Figueras, 2014; Gordon, 1997; Haack & Smith, 2000; Hamann et al., 1987; Hamann et al., 1988;

Hodge et al., 1994; Mancini, 2008; McLain, 2005; Nimmo, 1986; Sandene, 1995; Scheib, 2006; Varona, 2019). However, studies report that burnout differs according to branches and that music teachers experience more burnout than other branch teachers. For example, McLain (2005) determined that music teachers experienced more emotional exhaustion than other groups in her comparison of the results of five different teacher groups. Figueras (2014) comparing teacher burnout with national norms, similar to McLain's results, found that music teachers experienced higher levels of emotional exhaustion and depersonalization compared to norms. In the study conducted by Hodge et al. (1994) with music and mathematics teachers working in secondary schools, the levels of emotional disturbance and burnout of music teachers consisting of anxiety, depression, and distressing physical symptoms were significantly higher than math teachers. It is possible to support these examples with different studies (Hamann et al., 1987; Madsen & Hancock, 2002; NCfES, 1997; Nimmo, 1986; Robertson, 1986).

Burnout is discussed in some relevant research in Turkey. For example, Korkmaz (2004) found that music teachers experience medium level of burnout in emotional exhaustion and personal accomplishment and low level in depersonalization. In İnci and Burak's (2017) study; it is observed that music teachers experience medium level in emotional exhaustion, low level in depersonalization and high level in personal accomplishment. Some studies conducted by researchers outside of the field also present important findings. For example, in the study of Koruklu et al. (2012), it was determined that art and physical education teachers and music teachers experienced the medium level of burnout in emotional exhaustion and depersonalization and high level of personal accomplishment. According to the study, although no statistically significant difference was found, the burnout level of personal accomplishment dimension of music teachers was higher than 9 different branches. This finding is similar to the results of the relevant international literature. Karakuş (2008) found that although there is no statistically significant difference, the personal accomplishment perceptions of painting and music teachers are higher than classroom, science, and social studies teachers. In Şahin's (2007) study, it is seen that there is no significant difference between the burnout scores of music teachers and teachers from more than 10 different branches.

1.3 Purpose of the Study

This study carried out in Turkey is focused on the question; 'Does burnout of music teachers; differ according to gender, seniority, school-level worked and participation in in-service training programs?'¹. As can be understood from the summary of the literature, studies focus on organizational resources that cause burnout in music teachers. While "personal variables cannot be excluded in the analysis of burnout" (Dalkılıç, 2014, p. 88), it can be said that organizational factors have more significant effects on burnout than personal factors. Empirical research also provides strong evidence on this matter. On the other hand, individual characteristics may have an effect that increases or decreases burnout in the face of organizational factors that cause burnout in some cases (Ari & Bal, 2008; Örmən, 1993, cited in Dalkılıç, 2014, p. 77). However, studies that focus on the relationship between individual characteristics and burnout present inconsistent results, contrary to research on organizational factors. In other words, the relationship between teacher burnout and individual characteristics still remains uncertain. The uncertainty continues in the literature of music teaching. While the current situation supports the view that 'organizational factors are more effective on burnout' on the one hand, and on the other hand, it shows that there is a need for more findings that can clarify the uncertainty between individual characteristics and burnout. However, a precautionary approach is necessary to the relationship between burnout and individual variables (İnce, 2014; Sandene, 1995). Because some individual variables that affect behaviors, attitudes, and lifestyles can be shaped according to the culture in which they live. For example, teaching that is defined as a 'feminine profession' with its 'mother compassion' may turn into a profession that is very challenging and leads to burnout for women. In this sense, all research to be conducted in geographical regions with different dynamics can offer some clues that will help explain the relationship between individual characteristics of music teachers and burnout. This study focuses on demographic variables, one of the two dimensions of individual characteristics. Personality characteristics of the study group were not included in the study. In a provincial city, this narrow-scoped study conducted with a group of music teachers who work at

different educational levels and have different professional experience and equipment is expected to contribute to the related literature in Turkey.

Gender and seniority are the variables most studied in relevant national studies. The school-level worked is among the least processed. On the other hand, the variable of participating in in-service training, which is frequently discussed in teacher burnout studies, has been overlooked by researchers of the music field. Although nearly 30 variables were examined in the studies, it was not explained by which criteria the variables were determined. Based on the variables not determined for a certain purpose, the author argues that the relationship between burnout and individual variables should be addressed with an in-depth approach, not an in-beam approach in Turkey. For this reason, it would be meaningful to briefly explain the reason for choosing the variables discussed in this study, with the idea that it will also be beneficial for readers.

One of the most emphasized variables in disciplines that focus on individual and interpersonal relations, such as social psychology, organizational psychology, educational psychology, etc. is gender. The gender differences question, which has gained importance especially in educational research since the 1970s (Slavin, 2006) and is controversial (Figueras, 2014), also remains unclear in the burnout literature of music teachers. With Kertz-Welzel's (2009) statement; burnout affects male and female music teachers in different ways. Examining the gender variable, which is related to many factors such as personality structure, gender roles, culture, etc. in different contexts, may present some crumbling findings, especially for meta-analysis studies to be conducted on teacher burnout.

One of the field-specific factors that lead to burnout in music teachers is the praxis shock experienced in the early years of the profession. The international literature offers detailed and understandable findings on this subject. However, related research in Turkey has not addressed the seniority-praxis shock link. The seniority variable may give some clues about the presence of the praxis shock in music teachers in Turkey.

'Undesirable student behavior,' which is frequently observed in schools, is one of the main sources of teacher burnout today. Current ideological/political transformation has negatively affected music classes. Music lessons are the classes with the most discipline problems compared to most other branch classes. The discipline problem, which is related to many individual and environmental factors, manifests itself as different behavioral patterns according to age. The discipline problem, which manifests itself in different school levels, in different types and different severities, may also affect teachers' burnout in different ways.

In-service training programs are educational processes that contribute to teachers' professional and personal development. In-service training is an effective practice in the context of organizational measures that can be taken to prevent teacher burnout. It is known that music teachers who receive in-service training support experience less burnout than those who do not (McLain, 2005). Since 1960 in Turkey, although there have been some chronic problems in the development of professional music teacher, important strategic changes have been made by the Ministry of National Education in the field of in-service training in recent years (Öztürk, 2018; Ö. Öztürk & G. Öztürk, 2019). For this reason, current developments in the field of professional development necessitate the updating of in-service training programs and studies on burnout.

2. Method

This study is quantitative descriptive research structured according to the survey model. The purpose of survey models is the qualitative and quantitative description of the living, the existing, and what happened.

2.1 Study Group and Scope of Research

The working group consists of 48 permanent music teachers at central state schools in a province located in the central Black Sea region of Turkey. 50% of the study group is female and 50% is male; 41.7% of them work in

secondary schools, 27.1% in Fine Arts High School, 18.8% in high schools, and 12.5% in special education institutions; 12.5% have 1-5 years of professional experience, 35.4% have 6-10 years, again 35.4% have 11-15 years, 16.7% have 16 and more years; 35.4% of them participated in in-service training programs, 64.6% of them did not.

The research was supported by the Scientific Research Projects Commission of the university located in the same province (*project number: 2017/35*) and was carried out in cooperation with the Provincial Directorate of National Education. Since the research was conducted in a provincial province in terms of socio-economic structure, the results are not generalizable. However, the results obtained in this study; are considered to be comparable to the results of the research to be conducted in different cities with the same or similar characteristics as the city where the study was conducted.

2.2 Data Collection Tool

In the research, Maslach Burnout Inventory-Educators Survey (MBI-ES) developed by Maslach, Jackson, and Schwab (Maslach, Jackson, & Leiter, 1996) and adapted to Turkish by İnce and Şahin² (2015) was used. The survey consists of emotional exhaustion (EE), depersonalization (Dp), and personal accomplishment (PA) dimensions. Dp dimension of MBI-ES refers to the feeling of fatigue and exhaustion due to energy exhaustion; EE dimension indicates the educator's negative feelings and behaviors towards students; PA dimension expresses the sense of success experienced by the educator due to perceived competence and high productivity. The level of burnout is evaluated with three separate total scores from the dimensions instead of a single score. The total score for each dimension is obtained by collecting up the item scores. A single score is not obtained by combining the total scores of the dimensions. The inventory does not have any sub-dimensions to be scored backward (İnce & Şahin, 2015, p. 389). High scores in EE and Dp dimensions indicate high level of burnout, while a high score in PA dimension indicates low level of burnout (Figueras, 2014; Girgin, 1995; İnce & Şahin, 2015, p. 389; Maslach et al., 1996). PA dimension; can also be interpreted as a sense of lack of personal accomplishment or reduced personal accomplishment due to the inverse relationship between scoring and interpretation (İnce & Şahin, 2015).

In the form, corresponding to teachers' attitudes and behaviors; there are a total of 22 items, 9 in the EE dimension, 5 in the Dp dimension, and 8 in the PA dimension. The form is structured according to 7-Likert type grading. Degrees; is scored as '0-Never, 1-A few times a year or less, 2-Once a 461e efor461 less, 3-A few times a month, 4-Once a week, 5-A few times a week, 6-Every day'. The highest score that can be obtained in EE dimension is 54, 30 in Dp dimension, and 48 in PA dimension. The scores obtained from each dimension can be expressed as low, average, and high. The scores are interpreted that for EE, 27 and above is high, 17-26 is average, 0-16 is low; for Dp, 14 and above is high, 9-13 is average, 0-8 is low; for PA, 0-30 is high, 31-36 is average, 37 and above as low burnout (461e efor categories and numeric cutoff points; Bernhard, 2006, p. 8; Figueras, 2014, p. 113; İnce & Şahin, 2015, p. 390). It is especially recommended by Maslach et al. To use original numerical scores rather than categorization when performing statistical analysis (Figueras, 2014, p. 97).

2.3 Analysis of Data

Data were analyzed with SPSS software. Statistical hypothesis tests were applied to determine the univariate normality assumption. For this purpose, Shapiro-Wilk statistics analytical test values ($N < 30$) and skewness-kurtosis values of each data group were analyzed. In the literature ± 1 , ± 1.5 , ± 1.96 , ± 2 , ± 3 , ± 3.29 values are suggested for the assumption of normality. In this study, the ± 2 approach was taken into account in examining the skewness and kurtosis values (George & Mallery, 2019, p. 114-115). T-test and One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) for normally distributed data groups; Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis tests for data groups not normally distributed were used. For the significance level, $p < .05$ was taken as a reference.

3. Results

In this section, results showing whether the burnout of music teachers differs according to gender, seniority, school-level worked, and participation in in-service training are included.

3.1 Burnout Levels of Music Teachers according to the Gender

Table 1: Burnout and gender related t-test and Mann-Whitney U test results

Gender	n	Emotional Exhaustion	Depersonalization	Personal Accomplishment
		$\bar{X}$	$\bar{X}_{\text{rank}}$	$\bar{X}$
Female	24	14.46	22.38	37.42
Male	24	15.08	26.63	38.96
		t=-.2	U=237	t=-1.00
		p=.86	p=.28	p=.32

According to Table 1, emotional exhaustion ($t_{(46)}=-.25$ $p>.05$), depersonalization ($U=237$ $p>.05$) and personal accomplishment ($t_{(46)}=-1.00$ $p>.05$) scores of music teachers do not differ significantly according to gender.

3.2 Burnout Levels of Music Teachers according to the Seniority

Table 2: Burnout and seniority related ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis test results

Seniority	n	Emotional Exhaustion	Depersonalization	Personal Accomplishment
		$\bar{X}$	$\bar{X}_{\text{rank}}$	$\bar{X}$
1-5 years	6	7.83	28.83	40.17
6-10 years	17	16.24	24.24	37.47
11-15 years	17	14.94	25.47	37.76
16 and more years	8	16.50	19.75	39.12
		F=1.45	$\chi^2=1.68$	F=.48
		p=.24	p=.64	p=.70

According to Table 2, emotional exhaustion [$F_{(3,44)}=1.45$ $p>.05$], depersonalization [$\chi^2_{(3)}=1.68$ $p>.05$] and personal accomplishment [$F_{(3,44)}=.48$ $p>.05$] scores of music teachers do not differ significantly according to seniority. On the other hand, the emotional exhaustion ($\bar{X}=7.83$) and personal accomplishment ($\bar{X}=40.17$) score averages of the music teachers with 1-5 years of experience can be interpreted that they experienced lower levels of burnout compared to other groups and their personal accomplishment perception was higher.

3.3 Burnout Levels of Music Teachers according to the School-Level Worked

Table 3: Burnout and school-level worked related ANOVA and Kruskal-Wallis test results

School level	n	Emotional Exhaustion $\bar{X}$	Depersonalization $\bar{X}_{rank}$	Personal Accomplishment $\bar{X}$
Secondary	20	14.15	24.40	37.45
High school	9	14.56	22.67	37.78
High school of fine arts	13	15.38	27.04	38.46
Special education	6	15.83	22.08	40.67
		F=.08	$\chi^2=.81$	F=.57
		p=.97	p=.85	p=.64

According to Table 3, emotional exhaustion [$F_{(3-44)}=.08$ $p>.05$], depersonalization [$\chi^2_{(3)}=.81$ $p>.05$] and personal accomplishment [$F_{(3-44)}=.57$ $p>.05$] scores of music teachers do not differ significantly according to school-level worked.

3.4 Burnout Levels of Music Teachers according to the Participation in In-Service Training

Table 4: Burnout and participation in in-service training related t-test and Mann-Whitney U test results

In-service training	n	Emotional Exhaustion $\bar{X}$	Depersonalization $\bar{X}_{rank}$	Personal Accomplishment $\bar{X}$
Participated	17	15.12	26.74	37.88
Not participated	31	14.58	23.27	38.35
		t=.19	U=225.5	t=-.29
		p=.85	p=.34	p=.77

According to Table 4, emotional exhaustion ($t_{(46)}=.19$ $p>.05$), depersonalization (U=225.5 $p>.05$) and personal accomplishment ($t_{(46)}=-.29$ $p>.05$) scores of music teachers do not differ significantly according to participation in in-service training.

4. Discussion

In the study, it was found that emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and personal accomplishment scores of music teachers did not differ according to gender, seniority, school-level worked, and participation in in-service training. The results are discussed under separate headings according to the relevant variables.

4.1 Burnout and Gender

The question of gender differences, which remain uncertainty in the teacher burnout literature, is one of the most challenging discussion topics for researchers. It is possible to support the present result with some findings. In Turkey, in the studies conducted by Umuzdaş, Umuzdaş, and Baş (2015) and Karabulut (2019), it is observed that burnout of music teachers does not differ according to gender. Despite these results, Korkmaz (2004) reported that female teachers experienced more depersonalization than men, while Kılıç (2018) reported that female teachers' perception of personal accomplishment is lower than men's. Some studies originating from abroad also present similar results. For example, Gordon (1997) found that emotional and physical fatigue symptoms, which are indicators of burnout, are experienced significantly more in female music teachers. Hendry (2001) found that the depersonalization level of female teachers is higher than that of men. There are some studies showing that attrition, which is one of the sources of burnout, is more common in women (Hancock,

2008). Despite these findings, it would be meaningful to share two more study results. Figueras (2014) found that although there was no difference in depersonalization dimension, perceptions of emotional exhaustion and lack of personal accomplishment of male music teachers were higher than that of women. McLain (2005) reported that men have higher perceptions of depersonalization and lack of personal accomplishment than women. It is possible to support the results of Figueras and McLain with different studies (Hamann et al., 1988). Although the findings do not seem consistent, it can be said that there is a relative accumulation that female music teachers experience more burnout.

With the statement of Dođramacı (1997), the head of the family concept used for men in conventional structure in Turkey. Women, on the other hand, are responsible for childcare and housework. For this reason, women are expected to choose professions that do not interfere with their spouse and mother roles. Regardless of the education level of a woman, her participation in the workforce is significantly affected by housewife and mother roles. Despite this general acceptance in society, it is good to remind that one of the most important achievements of Atatürk's Turkey is 'women's rights.' It can be said that 'the teaching profession is the profession in which women take their first steps in social life in Turkey' (Dođramacı, 1997). In this sense, although it is a very criticized discourse, the author of this work considers the feminine label attributed to teaching in Turkey valuable. Because this reference is not an indication that female teachers are a group that has to choose to teach only because of their mother and spouse roles; it is also an indication that they are representative of contemporary education in Turkey. This duty attributed to female teachers means the handover of the role of 'Hatun,' representing gender equality in ancient Turks, to female teachers. This is why; teaching is one of the most preferred and loved professions by women in Turkey. On the other hand, the male-dominated structure of Turkish society reflected in social life requires female teachers to struggle with some difficulties in the professional process. In Kertz-Welzel's (2009) statement, there are certain aspects that distinguish female teachers' burnout from those of men. Professional and personal roles such as being a good wife and mother as well as being a good teacher are assigned to female teachers. On the other hand, female teachers often have different skills in resolving and dealing with conflicts. Female teachers have their unique teaching methods aim at a more understandable and creative environment and encourage students' personal and emotional development. Female teachers, who have a different position in schools because of these roles, tend to react to stress in different ways than men. However, in the current school system, female teachers cannot find suitable environments where they can implement their teaching skills. As in Turkey, a male-dominated and academic output-oriented school environment may sometimes not be a suitable place for female teachers to seek creativity and personal growth. This situation, which negatively affects socialization and leads to role conflict, can cause feelings of guilt and excessive demand among female teachers. This role conflict, which evolves into a cycle of self-wear and blame and results in emotional isolation, causes female music teachers to experience burnout.

Studies support the above view. However, our result is not in line with the results of empirical research. This situation can be attributed to the social, cultural, and economic structure of the city where the research was conducted. The city located in the inner part of the Central Black Sea Region differs from many in terms of socio-economic structure and dynamics such as employment, education, health, accessibility, quality of life, poverty, production, income, etc. according to the Socio-Economic Development Index (2013) and Middle Black Sea Development Agency (2014) Reports. The city, where the transformation from agriculture to the industry has not been achieved sufficiently, is well below the region and country average in terms of gross domestic product and other socio-economic development indicators (Barış, 2019). However, the city offers some advantages for female music teachers compared to metropolises. Metropolitan cities that demand a high cost-high income balance for a prosperous life can often be quite challenging for female teachers if there is no support of 'family elders'. The salary problem in the teaching profession is a problem that has been extending from the 1970s to the present. As can be seen in the relevant studies, teachers may have to do additional work to meet the minimum livelihood conditions, especially in big cities, due to the wage problem that causes loss of status and burnout. For female music teachers who are married and have children, this additional job means the addition of a new role Wezwel emphasized. In contrast, a female teacher's life in a provincial city can be relatively more economical provided that some social activities are compromised. Socio-economic factors are determinants of teacher burnout. According to Şahin's study (2007); teachers working in low socio-economic environments experience less burnout than those in high and medium socio-economic environments. As explained above,

although the city where the research was conducted means difficult living conditions for the local people, it is a preferable city in socio-economic terms for female teachers with a certain level of income. It is less costly for teachers to meet basic needs such as transportation, food, housing, etc. The city offers female music teachers a more comfortable life, especially in terms of transportation and time. In other words, although the roles and workloads of female music teachers working in metropolises and provinces are the same, it can be said that the teachers in the provinces focus better on their private lives. However, the city has a culture in which the traditional family structure relatively maintains its existence. This situation provides advantages for female music teachers in two ways. First, the status of female music teachers working in the city is at a more moderate point than in metropolitan cities. This position can have a reducing effect on burnout. On the other hand, considering that most of the female music teachers in the research group have family roots in this city, the city offers teachers a life where they can receive financial and moral support from 'elders.' Briefly, existing advantages may have created more field for female music teachers to resolve and manage conflicts between spouse, mother, and teacher roles and offset the impact of burnout sources for male and female teachers.

4.2 Burnout and Seniority

Research carried out in Turkey (Karabulut, 2019; Korkmaz, 2004; Umuzdaş et al., 2015) indicates that burnout in music teachers does not differ according to seniority. Despite these findings, Bernhard (2006) found that inexperienced music teachers experience more burnout than experienced teachers. Similarly, Figueras (2014) found that music teachers with less working years experience higher lack of personal accomplishment feelings than senior teachers. In a series of studies conducted by Hamann et al. and is firsts in the fields, it was determined that low-senior music teachers were more prone to burnout and experienced more burnout than senior teachers (Gordon, 1997; Hamann et al., 1987; Hamann et al., 1988). It can be said that the studies conducted at home and abroad provide consistent results in themselves. On the other hand, the result can be interpreted that in Turkey, music teachers were not exposed to praxis shock and/or burnout due to praxis shock is not experienced intensely.

One of the main problems leading to burnout in music teachers is the lack of methodological/pedagogical knowledge and skills arising from the workload and pre-service education. These problems are also the main sources of the praxis shock that new music teachers are exposed to. For example, in a large-scale study (Cross, 2016), 34% of music teachers showed workload as a source of burnout. The literature offers a lot of evidence on this subject. In Turkey, it is known that music teachers do not experience burnout due to workload, but there are some problems with pre-service training (Öztürk & Öztürk, 2020). The effect of praxis shock on burnout is related to the nature of the organizational measures taken. Because, as Ballantyne (2005) summarized, the praxis shock is an important element that determines a teacher's attitude towards teaching, understanding of the profession, in-classroom practices, and whether s/he will stay in the profession for a long time. In this context, the result can be attributed to the in-service training strategy developed by the Ministry of National Education in recent years and effectively implemented by the Provincial Directorate of National Education. Teachers who have started to attend classes directly after being appointed can enter the lessons after going through a training period. Newly recruited teachers receive a total of 654 hours of training, including classroom and in-school activities, out-of-school activities, and in-service training activities. The predominant part of the training consists of classroom observations, meeting with experienced colleagues, following academic and other publications, etc. Formal and informal environments are offered with many participation where teachers can share on entrepreneurship, motivation, combating cultural differences, career planning, and current practices during the candidacy process. This process is further strengthened with the support received from the university and some other institutions and organizations in the city (Ağar, 2017). In addition to formal activities, it is known that informal environments that allow teachers to share professionally among themselves are an effective professional development practice (Koner & Eros, 2019). Briefly; it is thought that this strategy of integration into the profession, carried out in well-planned environments and well-structured practices, reduces the effects of the praxis shock expected in music teachers in the first years of the profession and this effect is reflected in the result on hand.

4.3 Burnout and School-Level Worked

Relevant studies examining the relationship between burnout and the school-level worked studied present different results. In a study conducted in the USA, it was reported that 56% of music teachers working in middle schools experienced burnout and this rate was higher than teachers working in elementary schools (50%), high schools (50%), and colleges (43%) (Cross, 2016). Similarly, Bernhard (2006) found that although there is no statistically significant difference, the perceptions of emotional exhaustion, depersonalization, and lack of personal accomplishment of music teachers working in secondary schools are higher than teachers working in high schools and primary schools. It is possible to support these examples with different studies (Gordon, 1997; Hamann, 1989, cited in Gordon, 2000, p. 28-29; Varona, 2019). The findings presented show that the secondary school-level is the determinant of burnout. On the other hand, Korkmaz (2004) found that burnout of music teachers did not differ according to school-level worked in a study she conducted in a metropolis. Similarly, Hamann (1986, cited in Gordon, 1997, p. 37) found that music teachers at all levels are prone to burnout. Our result does not correspond to most research results. This situation can be attributed to the differences in practice regarding music education in the countries where the studies were conducted. For example; while in European and North American countries, music teachers teach in primary schools as well as high school and secondary schools, music teachers work only in secondary and high school levels in Turkey. On the other hand, the socio-economic/socio-cultural structure of the countries and the nature of the organizational measures taken may have different effects on the results. It is known that there is a need for national studies where we can discuss the subject in Turkey. However, it is possible to link the present result to some factors.

One of the most important sources of teacher burnout is undesirable student behavior. Today, many countries are dealing with the discipline problem in schools. For example, in Turkey, teachers are divided into approximately 27% of class time to maintain the order in classroom and administrative affairs (TEDMEM, 2019). According to the reports of the Ministry of National Education, most of the teachers demand in-service training on new approaches in education and educational technologies as well as guidance, conflict and stress management, communication skills, problem-solving techniques, classroom management, etc. (Ministry of National Education [MoNE], 2013, 2014). In other words, for teachers to guide students, they first need guidance on classroom and stress management issues. These expectations should be considered as clues to the existence of a disciplinary problem. As emphasized in the conceptual framework, the devaluation of school music education has led to a further increase in undesirable student behavior in music classes. According to the report of Cross (2016), 64% of the new music teachers reported disciplinary problems as a source of burnout. Indifference, negative behavior and attitudes of students, low motivation to learn in students are common sources of stress for music teachers and need to be addressed through in-service training (Gordon, 1997; Hamann & Daugherty, 1985; McLain, 2005; Sandene, 1995). However, in Turkey, it is known that the in-service training programs organized for music teachers could not meet the guidance demands of teachers in terms of stress and classroom management, therefore participants in in-service training activities developed negative attitudes towards the programs. In short terms; the tendency to resist authority and work discipline, which is seen in high school students and is one of the most distinctive behavioral patterns of adolescence (Andrews, 1996), has become widespread in lower levels today. This situation manifests itself clearly in music lessons. In-service training activities ignore this expansion in the discipline. In this context, the result can be attributed to the prevalence of the discipline problem in music classes at all levels and the structuring of in-service training programs without considering the issue of guidance.

4.4 Burnout and In-Service Training

International literature also deals with burnout in music teachers within the framework of professional development programs. However, the relationship between in-service training and the burnout of the music teachers in Turkey has been ignored. In this sense, the result can offer some ideas on this matter. Two studies on the subject are particularly noteworthy. In a study conducted by McLain (2005) with 514 music teachers, it was determined that professional development programs are the determinants of burnout in music teachers. The researcher reported that music teachers who are not satisfied with their professional development opportunities experience more emotional exhaustion and depersonalization than those who are satisfied. Gordon (1997), on the

other hand, determined that music teachers who work in urban experience higher and significant burnout in professional development than those in non-urban. The present result does not exactly match the limited number of findings. This is due to the quality of in-service training programs in Turkey.

As Koner and Eros (2019) stated; music teachers have varying professional development needs throughout their careers, and needs may be influenced by their professional experience. The need for development necessitates the revision of professional development programs. Because in-service training practices are one of the most effective organizational measures that can be taken in reducing burnout. In Turkey, two recent studies on the in-service training needs of music teachers, the expectations and regulated programs, offer some observations on the subject. The current system does not provide an effective professional development opportunity for music teachers, similar to professional socialization programs applied to new teachers. Programs for music teachers are insufficient in terms of number and content. It is seen that between the years of 2007-2017 in Turkey, nearly 7500 in-service training activities are organized by the Ministry of National Education, only 27 of these activities target music teachers, the activities focus on the promotion of the relevant teaching programs and the subjects aimed at the personal development of music teachers are ignored (Öztürk, 2018; G. Öztürk & Ö. Öztürk, 2019). The current situation, as reflected in the reports, leads the teachers to remain relatively low rates of participation in the in-service training program in accordance with European countries. Based on current findings; the result is thought to be related to the quality of the in-service training programs organized for music teachers.

Epilogue

Burnout was included in academic studies in North America in the 1970s. It has been addressed in the field of international music teaching since the early 1980s. It entered the national literature in the 1990s. During the 2000s, it has attracted the attention of researchers in the field of music education in Turkey. Thus, it can be said that the literature on music teacher burnout in Turkey needs to be maturation. In this context, it is recommended to conduct generalizable, well-structured, comprehensive, and well-attended studies throughout Turkey with research groups to be established at universities, via the modules offered by the Ministry of National Education for teachers. The data to be obtained at the end of these studies will partially close the gap in the national literature in a short time and contribute to the organizational measures to be taken nationally and regionally.

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Notes

Note 1. Burnout data of the study group was processed in a different study (Öztürk & Öztürk, 2020) in the context of the presence or absence status of burnout in music teachers in Turkey. For this reason, in this study, the findings regarding the absolute level of burnout were not presented. However, burnout levels were used to draw attention to some of the findings of this study and to make the comments more understandable. For this purpose, information about the cut-off points of the scale is specifically presented in the method section.

Note 2. The author would like to thank Nuri Barış İnce and Ali Ekber Şahin for approving the scale used in this research.